

THE ROLE OF SELF-REGULATION IN COPING WITH ENGLISH TEST ANXIETY: A STUDY IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The role of test anxiety and self-regulated language learning has long been a topic of interest and research. Studies have shown that individuals with high anxiety levels have low levels of self-regulated learning (Romera and de la Fuente, 2021). From this perspective, this study explores the relationship between English test anxiety level and self-regulating capacity in language learning. A correlational research design was employed, with 127 participants utilizing two survey questionnaires: to assess students' test anxiety levels and evaluate their self-regulating capacity in language learning. Findings revealed that participants exhibited high self-regulation in language learning, alongside high levels of test anxiety. Pearson's correlation test showed no significant relationship between students' overall self-regulating capacity and their test anxiety levels in terms of worry and total level of anxiety. However, a significant relationship was found between specific self-regulation aspects in terms of commitment control, satiation control, environment control, and the level of test anxiety related to emotionality. These findings suggest that while general self-regulation skills do not directly impact test anxiety, targeted aspects of self-regulation play a role in managing emotional responses to testing situations. To support students in sustaining their self-regulation and coping with test anxiety, this study recommends a policy-based modified resilience framework for learners, training programs for educators and stakeholders, and a year-long intervention

program. This would help students strengthen their self-regulation in language learning, build resilience, and stay productive despite academic challenges.

Keywords: *English test anxiety level, intervention program, language learning, self-regulating capacity, test anxiety.*

INTRODUCTION

Test anxiety is a significant factor that influences students' academic performance, as it encompasses negative physiological, emotional, and cognitive responses to examinations. Symptoms such as increased heart rate, rapid breathing, and excessive worry about failing can manifest before, during, or after an assessment (Howard, 2020). Consequently, test anxiety negatively affects students' academic performance by triggering physiological, emotional, and cognitive distress before, during, or after exams. Moreover, if not addressed, anxiety in education can hinder productivity, lower educational performance, and even lead to physical health issues (Mukhlis et al., 2020). On the other hand, minimal anxiety may also result in poor performance due to a lack of preparation (Jerrim, 2022). Thus, balancing test anxiety levels is crucial for optimal academic outcomes.

Academic achievement is highly valued in today's educational system, as it reflects whether students have met the intended learning objectives (Kumari, 2020). More specifically, success in academic performance measures students' understanding of the subject matter and the effectiveness of instructional strategies. To ensure this, educators administer examinations as a form of assessment. According to Pachaiappan et al. (2023), exams serve multiple purposes, including assessing students' knowledge, determining eligibility for higher education, and holding teachers and institutions accountable. Furthermore, examinations provide a basis for analyzing learning success rates and identifying factors that may impact students' performance.

Among the different emotions experienced by English as a foreign language learner, positive emotions play a crucial role in enhancing self-regulation, which is closely linked to emotion, behavior, and long-term academic success (Li et al., 2024). Similarly, Yin (2020) highlighted the connection between self-regulation, emotions, and academic performance, emphasizing the importance of emotional conditioning in fostering self-regulation skills. In this regard, self-regulation is another critical factor that influences learning. It involves goal setting, time management, strategic learning approaches, self-evaluation, motivation, seeking help, and personal beliefs about academic success (Pahuriray, 2021). In support of this, Barber et al. (2023) stressed that self-regulation significantly impacts students' ability to learn, while Miller (2022) found that students who align their learning styles with their instructors' teaching methods are more likely to succeed. Indeed, one's learning process is essential for academic achievement as it enables students to take an active role in their education. Notably, a strong relationship exists between high test anxiety and poor study skills, with unprepared students experiencing greater levels of anxiety (Pahuriray, 2021). By this, Morosanova and Fomina

(2017) suggested that students who develop conscious self-regulation strategies are more likely to succeed in exams.

Given these insights, this study aimed to determine the participants' self-regulating capacity in language learning and evaluate whether their self-regulating capacity has a significant relationship to their test anxiety level in English. Ultimately, the findings of this study would serve as a foundation for designing an intervention program to help students improve their self-regulation skills and manage test anxiety effectively. Therefore, the results of this research would be valuable for teachers, parents, learners, researchers, and school administrators.

Research Questions

This study primarily aimed to determine the students' self-regulated capacity in language learning and the level of test anxiety among Grade 7,8, and 9 students of Cahayagan National High School. Specifically, this study would like to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of self-regulated language learning capacity of the participants when taken as a whole and in terms of:
 - 1.1. commitment control;
 - 1.2. metacognition control;
 - 1.3. satiation control;
 - 1.4. emotion control, and
 - 1.5. environment control?
2. What are the anxiety levels of students in English tests in terms of:
 - 2.1 worry;
 - 2.2 emotionality; and
 - 2.3 total anxiety?
3. Is there a relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English tests?
4. Based on the data gathered, what intervention program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This presents the research design, research locale, participants, procedure for collecting data, data quantification, and the statistical treatment utilized for analyzing the gathered data.

Research Design

The study employed a correlational research design. The design utilized in this study determined the relationship between the level of self-regulated capacity in language learning and the test anxiety level of Grade 7,8, and 9 Junior High School students of

Cahayagan National High School without making any interference. The study utilized two standardized questionnaires. The first questionnaire determined the test anxiety level of the participants in terms of worry and emotionality. On the other hand, the second questionnaire identified the level of the participants' self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment, metacognition, satiation, emotion, and environment control.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Cahayagan National High School, located in Cahayagan, Carmen, Agusan del Norte. Established in 2005, the school has been a key secondary educational institution in the municipality, catering to junior and senior high school students from various barangays in the area. It offers a comprehensive curriculum aimed at fostering academic excellence, including a strong emphasis on English language learning. With its supportive learning environment, experienced faculty, and diverse student population, Cahayagan National High School serves as an ideal setting for investigating self-regulated language learning and test anxiety in English assessments. The participants of this study were the 127 Grade 7,8, and 9 students of Cahayagan National High School in junior high.

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were the 127 Grade 7, 8, and 9 students of Cahayagan National High School, as shown in the given table. The Grade 7, 8, and 9 students were the participants of the study since they are in a critical stage of language learning where self-regulation and test anxiety significantly impact their academic performance. The Junior high school serves as a transition period where students develop foundational English skills and face increasingly complex assessments that can trigger test anxiety. At this stage, students also begin to develop metacognitive strategies and self-awareness, making it an ideal period to examine their self-regulating capacity in language learning. Additionally, their exposure to structured English tests provides a relevant context for analyzing how anxiety affects their learning behaviors. Understanding their experiences will help in designing appropriate intervention programs to support their academic and emotional well-being as they prepare for senior high school.

Instruments of the Study

The study used two standardized questionnaires to test the students' test anxiety levels, and the second was for self-regulating capacity in language learning. The Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI), adapted from Charles D. Spielberger (1980), was used to test the anxiety level of the students. The TAI questionnaire was composed of 20 items that used a four-point Likert scale for each item, where (1) – almost never, (2) – sometimes, (3) – often, and (4) – almost always. It contains three subscales: Test Anxiety-Total (TAI-T), Test Anxiety-Worry (TAIW), and Test Anxiety-Emotionality (TAI-E). Eight items of the Test Anxiety Inventory measure the TAI-W (# 3,4,5,6,7,14,17, and 20), eight items measure TAI-E (# 2,8,9,10,11,15,16, and 18), and the remaining four for measuring TAI-

T (# 1,12,13, and 19). The second instrument was an adopted questionnaire from Liu (2020) to evaluate the student's Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning. It contained 27 questions, nine items for commitment control (# 3, 4, 7, 10, 12, 18, 21, 22, 24, and 26), 6 for metacognition control (# 5, 9, 11, 14, 20, and 27), 4 for satiation control (# 1, 8, 15, and 16), 6 for emotion control (# 2, 6, 13, 19, 23, and 25) and 2 for environment control (# 3 and 17). It uses the 4- Likert scale that ranges from "disagree," "slightly disagree," "slightly agree," and "agree."

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the validity and reliability of the research questionnaire, the researchers adapted the research instrument and submitted a copy of the adapted questionnaire to the psychologist and guidance counselor, whose expertise is relevant to self-regulation in coping with English Test Anxiety. After retrieving the comments and suggestions from the experts, the researchers then presented and gathered the data from the participants. Then the data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted by a statistician for their reliability coefficient.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study employed the following strategies in data gathering:

Entry Protocol Phase. Before conducting the study, the researchers sent a letter of permission to the school head to survey the grade 7, 8, and 9 students of Cahayagan National High School.

Administration and Retrieval Phase. The questionnaires were personally handed out and administered by the researchers. Before administering the questionnaires, the researchers conducted an orientation on what the research was all about; after the administration, the researchers collected the test questionnaire.

Organization Phase. The researchers gathered the participants' responses and consolidated the data.

Data Interpretation Phase. After organizing the participants' responses, the data were submitted to a statistician for data analysis.

Statistical Treatment

The study used the following statistical tools to analyze the data:

Mean. This statistical tool determines the level of anxiety and self-regulating capacity in the language learning of the participants.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient. This was utilized to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the participants' self-regulatory skills and English test anxiety.

RESULTS

This presents the data gathered through the research instrument used in the study. It provides presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data in graphs and tables with textual explanation.

Research Question 1. What is the level of self-regulated language learning capacity of the participants when taken as a whole and in terms of: commitment control, metacognition control, satiation control, emotion control, and environment control?

Table 1 presents the mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment control.

The standardized questionnaire consists of 27 questions, and to get the level of commitment control, there are nine items to answer; these items are numbers 10, 4, 12, 22, 24, 7, 26, 18, and 21; the rest of the items indicate the other self-regulating capacity. Table 2 also shows the item numbers and indicators, and the verbal description and interpretation of the mean. Specifically, the indicators are the questions that assess the participants' commitment control level. Furthermore, the verbal description is based on the mean that ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree, which is then interpreted from very high to very low levels of self-regulating capacity in language learning.

Table 1 shows the highest and lowest mean scores in the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment control. The highest mean score is 3.30, which corresponds to Item 12, stating, "I believe I can overcome all the difficulties in English learning and achieve my English learning goals." This indicator has a verbal description of "Agree" and an interpretation of "High," suggesting that students strongly believe in their ability to overcome challenges and succeed in learning English. Following this, Item 24 has a mean score of 3.18, where students agree that they can effectively solve problems encountered during the learning process. Item 26 comes next, with a 3.14 mean score, showing that students know how to speed up their learning progress when falling behind. Item 10 follows with 2.96, indicating that learners persist until they reach their self-set goals. Both Item 4 and Item 22 have a mean score of 2.94, reflecting those students have special techniques to achieve their learning objectives and know how to maintain their concentration. Item 7 scored 2.89, showing that students believe they can achieve their learning goals faster than expected. Meanwhile, Item 18 has a mean score of 2.58, indicating that students agree they do not allow anything to interfere with their planned learning schedule. The lowest mean score is 2.47, seen in Item 21, which states, "When I studied English in the past, I often gave up halfway during the learning process." This indicator falls under "Disagree" and is interpreted as "Low," suggesting that most students did not relate to giving up on learning English in the past. The overall average mean score is 2.93, which falls under the "Agree" category, indicating that students generally have a high level of commitment control in their English learning.

The overall mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in learning English in terms of commitment control is 2.93 and is interpreted as high. This implies that the participants have high commitment control in language learning. Çelebi-Özkul (2020) found that the strength of young people and learners' commitment to the goal will affect how much they will strive to achieve the goal. Similarly, Kizilcec et al. (2017) discovered that learners with higher levels of commitment demonstrated higher levels of self-regulated learning strategies and desirable achievement. This achievement includes having desirable scores in assessments.

Table 1

Mean Distribution of The Level of Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning in Terms of Commitment Control.

Item no.	Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
12	I believe I can overcome all the difficulties in English learning and achieve my English learning goals	3.30	Agree	High
24	When learning English, I can effectively solve the problems I encounter during the learning process.	3.18	Agree	High
26	When I am behind my English learning schedule; I know how to speed up my learning progress.	3.14	Agree	High
10	When learning English, I persist until I reach the goals that I make for myself.	2.96	Agree	High
4	When learning English, I have my special techniques to achieve my learning objectives	2.94	Agree	High
22	When studying English, I know how to maintain my concentration.	2.94	Agree	High
7	When leaning English, I believe I can achieve my goals more quickly than expected.	2.89	Agree	High
18	When I study English, I do not allow anything to interfere with my already-planned learning schedule	2.58	Agree	High
21	When I studied English in the past, I often gave up halfway during the learning process	2.47	Disagree	Low
Average		2.93	Agree	High

Ranges of Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

Table 2

Mean Distribution of The Level of Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning in Terms of Metacognition

Item no.	Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
9	When learning English, I think my methods of controlling my concentration are effective.	3.13	Agree	High
5	When studying English, I have my special techniques to keep my concentration focused.	3.09	Agree	High
27	When studying English, I am easily distracted.	3.08	Agree	High
14	When it comes to learning English, I think my methods of controlling procrastination is effective.	2.86	Agree	High
11	When it comes to learning English, I have my special techniques to prevent procrastination.	2.76	Agree	High
20	When it comes to studying English, I tend to procrastinate the learning.	2.53	Agree	High
Average		2.99	Agree	High

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

Table 2 shows the highest and lowest mean scores in the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of metacognition control. The highest mean score is 3.13, which corresponds to Item 9, stating, "When learning English, I think my methods of controlling my concentration are effective." This indicator has a verbal description of "Agree" and an interpretation of "High," suggesting that students believe they have effective ways to maintain their concentration while learning English. Following this, Item 5 has a mean score of 3.09, where students agree that they have special techniques to keep their focus. Item 27 comes next, with a 3.08 mean score, indicating that students recognize being easily distracted when studying English. Item 14 follows with 2.86, reflecting that student think their methods of controlling procrastination are effective. Meanwhile, Item 11 has a mean score of 2.76, showing that students have special techniques to prevent procrastination in learning. The lowest mean score is 2.53, seen in Item 20, which states, "When it comes to studying English, I tend to procrastinate the learning." Although this indicator has the lowest score, it still falls under "Agree" and is interpreted as "High," suggesting that some students acknowledge their tendency to delay studying. The overall average mean score is 2.99, which falls under the "Agree" category, indicating that students generally have a high level of metacognitive control in their English learning process.

These findings align with the results presented in the study, particularly in terms of metacognition control. The data shows that students agree they have special techniques to maintain their concentration while studying English, as seen in the highest-rated indicators. This supports Litualy's (2020) assertion that learning strategies play a crucial role in keeping students focused. However, the findings also reveal that some students acknowledge being easily distracted and struggling with procrastination, which corresponds with Rahimi et al.'s (2021) argument that procrastination is linked to academic emotions. The lowest-rated indicator, where students admit to procrastinating their studies, further supports the claim that negative emotions, such as anxiety, contribute to delays in academic tasks. Therefore, these related studies reinforce the idea that both effective learning techniques and emotional regulation significantly influence students' self-regulation in language learning.

Table 3 presents the mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of satiation control. A standardized questionnaire is used to test the level of satiation control of the participants, and out of 27 questions, four (4) specific questions will assess the level of satiation control; these items are numbers 1, 8, 15, and 16. Moreover, Table 4 presents the item numbers, indicators, verbal descriptions, and mean interpretation. The indicators are the questions assessing the participants' satisfaction control level. The overall average or mean will test the level of the participant's self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of satiation control.

Table 3

Mean Distribution of The Level of Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning in Terms of Satiation Control

Item no.	Questions	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
16	When feeling bored with learning English, I know how to regulate my mood to invigorate the learning process	2.97	Agree	High
8	I feel satisfied with the methods I use to eliminate the boredom in studying English.	2.90	Agree	High
15	During the process of learning English, I am confident that I can overcome any sense of boredom	2.89	Agree	High
1	Once the novelty of learning English is gone, I easily become impatient about it.	2.23	Disagree	Low
Average		2.86	Agree	High

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

The table shows the highest to the lowest mean scores in terms of self-regulating capacity in language learning related to satiation control. The highest mean score is for item number 16, with a mean of 2.97, a verbal description of "Agree," and a high interpretation. This indicator states, "When feeling bored with learning English, I know how to regulate my mood to invigorate the learning process," which suggests that learners generally believe they can manage their emotions to stay engaged. The second highest is item number 8, with a mean score of 2.90, also interpreted as high, stating, "I feel satisfied with the methods I use to eliminate the boredom in studying English." This implies that learners are confident in their strategies to combat boredom. Following closely, item number 15 has a mean score of 2.89, with a similar interpretation of high, indicating that "During the process of learning English, I am confident that I can overcome any sense of boredom." This means that learners trust their ability to persist despite moments of dullness. Lastly, item number 1 has the lowest mean score of 2.23, interpreted as low, with a verbal description of "Disagree." The statement, "Once the novelty of learning English is gone, I easily become impatient about it," suggests that most learners do not feel they lose interest easily once the excitement of learning fades. Overall, the average mean score of 2.86 falls under the "Agree" category, indicating that learners generally perceive themselves as capable of managing boredom effectively while learning English.

Bayraktar (2021) stated that satiation control involves adding extra attraction to tasks and managing boredom, highlighting the need for students to be trained in handling boredom while learning. Judit (2017) supported this by emphasizing that learners tend to find alternative ways to stay engaged, such as working faster to finish sooner or taking breaks before continuing. This aligns with the study's findings, which suggest that when learners experience boredom, they actively seek ways to regulate it. Eastwood et al. (2019) described boredom as an unpleasant emotion that signals the need for increased engagement and encourages individuals to seek new sources of stimulation. Additionally, boredom can motivate students to adopt positive coping behaviors, but it is also linked to negative mental health and academic consequences (Eastwood et al., 2019). Frequent boredom has been associated with depression, anxiety, substance addiction, and a reduced quality of life (Chin et al., 2017). The participants' disagreement on impatience suggests that they are aware of the importance of managing boredom while learning English, as failing to do so could hinder their academic performance and assessment outcomes. The overall mean score of 2.86 indicates a high level of self-regulating capacity in language learning regarding satiation control. However, Çepni (2021) noted that among the subscales of self-regulating capacity, satiation control—referring to managing boredom while studying—was the least agreed upon. The descriptive statistics indicate that students still require training in coping with boredom. Nonetheless, the results demonstrate that the participants recognize the importance of self-regulation in overcoming boredom.

Table 4

Mean Distribution of The Level of Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning in Terms of Environment Control

Item No.	Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
3	When I study English, I look for a good learning environment.	3.33	Agree	High
17	When I am studying English and the learning environment becomes unsuitable, I try to sort out the problem.	3.02	Agree	High
Average		3.41	Agree	High

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

Table 4 presents the highest to the lowest mean scores regarding the level of self-regulating capacity in learning English in terms of environment control. The highest mean score is for item number 3, with a mean of 3.33, a verbal description of "Agree," and a high interpretation. This indicator states, "When I study English, I look for a good learning environment," suggesting that learners actively seek an environment conducive to effective studying. The next highest item, number 17, has a mean score of 3.02, also interpreted as high, indicating that "When I am studying English and the learning environment becomes unsuitable, I try to sort out the problem." This implies that learners make efforts to adjust their surroundings when faced with distractions or an unfavorable study environment. Overall, the mean score of 3.41 suggests that learners generally agree that they regulate their learning environment to enhance their ability to study English effectively.

According to Usman et al. (2019), a learning environment equipped with accessible amenities enhances the teaching and learning process, ultimately leading to student academic success. This suggests that a student's performance, knowledge retention, and learning acquisition are influenced by their surroundings. Mohamad (202) supported this by emphasizing that the learning environment impacts students' behavior and learning as both are considered responses to environmental factors. However, Mohamad also found that the learning environment had an insignificant effect on students' academic engagement. With an overall mean of 3.41, the participants agreed that environmental control plays a role in their language learning process, indicating a high level of environmental regulation. Bahrami (2022) reinforced this by stating that self-regulating strategies employed by students significantly impact both personal and environmental factors in their use of self-regulated learning strategies. On the other hand, Tseng (2006) noted that environment control had a slightly lower value than other self-regulation components, although all measures remained within a satisfactory range. Additionally, student involvement in the learning environment is essential for academic engagement, which aligns with the theory presented in this study, emphasizing that the learning environment influences students' learning and behavior (Lipoff, 2018)

Research Question 2. What are the anxiety levels of students in English tests in terms of worry, emotionality, and total anxiety?

Table 6 shows the anxiety level of the participants in English tests in terms of worry. It includes the item numbers, questions, mean, verbal description, and interpretation. To determine the level of test anxiety among the participants, a standardized questionnaire with 20 questions was used, and in terms of worry, it consisted of eight questions. These are item numbers 20, 4, 14, 3, 5, 7, 17, and 6. Additionally, the item numbers presented in Table 7 are arranged from highest to lowest mean, with a verbal description from always almost to almost never, and with an interpretation from very high to very low.

Table 6

Mean Distribution of The Level of Test Anxiety in English in Terms of Worry

Item no.	Questions	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
20	During examinations, I get so nervous that I forget facts I really know.	2.82	Often	High
17	During tests, I find myself thinking about the consequences of failing.	2.80	Often	High
14	I seem to defeat myself while working on important tests	2.77	Often	High
3	Thinking about my grade in a course interferes with my work on tests.	2.76	Often	High
5	During exams, I find myself thinking I will get through the school	2.65	Often	High
7	Thoughts of doing poorly interfere with my concentration on tests.	2.62	Often	High
6	The harder I work at taking a test, the more confused I get.	2.46	Sometimes	Low
4	I freeze up on important exam	2.40	Sometimes	Low
Average		2.73	Often	High

Ranges of Mean: 1.00-1.49-Almost Never; 1.50-2.49-Sometimes; 2.50-3.49-Often; 3.50-4.00-Almost always

The table presents the level of test anxiety in English in terms of worry, ranked from the highest to the lowest mean score. The highest mean score is from item number 20, which has a mean of 2.82, a verbal description of “Often,” and a high interpretation. This indicator reflects those students frequently experience nervousness during examinations to the point of forgetting facts they genuinely know. Following closely is item number 17, with a mean of 2.80, indicating that students often think about the consequences of failing while taking a test. Item number 14, with a mean of 2.77, shows that many students feel as though they defeat themselves when working on important tests. Similarly, item number 3, with a mean of 2.76, suggests that concerns about grades often interfere with students’ performance during tests. Meanwhile, item number 5, with a mean of 2.65, and item number 7, with a mean of 2.62, indicate that students frequently worry about whether they will get through school and that thoughts of doing poorly impact their concentration during tests. However, items 6 and 4, with mean scores of 2.46 and 2.40, respectively, received a verbal description of “Sometimes” and a low interpretation, indicating that fewer students experience confusion due to effort and freezing up during

exams. The overall mean score of 2.73 suggests that students often experience test anxiety related to worry, which is interpreted as high. The overall weighted mean of 2.73 indicates that learners “often” worry about their exams and tests. This suggests that they frequently feel concerned about their performance, often experience nervousness, and sometimes freeze up. In this context, learners demonstrate an awareness of the consequences of their actions and emotions, with anxiety stemming from the worry they carry. However, several studies argue that test anxiety is not a significant factor in negatively affecting students’ learning outcomes (Brady et al., 2018; Amy, 2017; Alicia, 2018).

Achanan et.al. (2021) emphasized that anxiety, low motivation, inhibition, introversion, and low self-esteem contribute to mental blocks, creating an affective filter that hinders learners from acquiring the comprehensible input necessary for second language competency. This suggests that even if students prepare for exams, anxiety can overwhelm them, leading to forgetfulness due to nervousness affecting their cognitive function. Tanner (2017) explained that when students are allowed to experience confusion, they develop the ability to think critically and apply metacognition. This implies that critical thinking and metacognition become effective when learners experience confusion.

Table 7
Mean Distribution of The Level of Test Anxiety in English in Terms of Emotionality

Item no.	Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
2	While taking examinations, I have an uneasy, upset feeling.	2.89	Often	High
8	I feel very jittery when taking an important test.	2.79	Often	High
10	I start feeling very uneasy just before getting a test paper back.	2.77	Often	High
11	During tests, I feel very tense.	2.72	Often	High
18	I feel my heart beating very fast during important tests.	2.70	Often	High
9	Even when I am well prepared for a test, I feel very nervous	2.69	Often	High
15	I feel very panicky when I take an important test.	2.69	Often	High
16	I worry a great deal before taking an important examination.	2.69	Often	High
	Average	2.80	Often	High

Ranges of Mean: 1.00-1.49-Almost Never. 1.50-2.49-Sometimes. 2.50-3.49-Often. 3.50-4.00-Almost always

The table presents the highest to the lowest mean scores related to anxiety in learning English in terms of emotionality. The highest mean score is 2.89 for item number 2, with a verbal description of “often” and a high interpretation. This indicator suggests that learners frequently experience an uneasy and upset feeling while taking examinations. Following this, item number 8 has a mean score of 2.79, indicating that students often feel jittery when taking an important test. Similarly, item number 10, with a mean score of 2.77, reflects that those learners start feeling very uneasy just before receiving their test papers back. Item number 11, with a mean of 2.72, suggests that students often feel very tense during tests. Meanwhile, item number 18, which has a mean score of 2.70, shows that learners often experience a rapid heartbeat during important tests. Furthermore, item numbers 9, 15, and 16 all share a mean score of 2.69, indicating that even when well-prepared, students often feel nervous, panicky and worry a great deal before taking an important examination.

The overall mean score of 2.80 indicates that participants “often” experience emotional anxiety during tests. This suggests that test-taking situations frequently induce nervousness, uneasiness, and worry among students, which can affect their performance and emotional well-being. This result suggests that participants exhibit a high level of test anxiety in terms of emotionality. According to Tang et.al (2024), they examined either the physical or psychological symptoms of anxiety separately without considering their interaction. This suggests that anxiety is not limited to emotional responses but also involves physical symptoms such as shaky hands and an upset stomach. However, numerous studies indicate that while anxiety may influence students, it is not necessarily the primary factor contributing to poor learning outcomes (Brady et al., 2018).

Table 8
Mean Distribution of The Level of Test Anxiety in English in Terms of Total Anxiety

Item No.	Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
12	I wish examinations did not bother me so much.	2.77	Often	High
19	After an exam is over, I try to stop worrying about it, but I just can't.	2.62	Often	High
13	During important tests, I am so tense that my stomach gets upset.	2.49	Sometimes	Low
1	I feel confident and relaxed while taking tests.	2.48	Sometimes	Low
Average		2.69	Often	High

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Almost Never, 1.50-2.49-Sometimes, 2.50-3.49-Often, 3.50-4.00-Almost always

The table shows the highest to the lowest mean scores related to test anxiety in learning English. The highest mean score is from item number 12, which obtained a mean of 2.77, with a verbal description of “often” and a high interpretation. This indicator states, “I wish examinations did not bother me so much,” suggesting that participants frequently experience anxiety related to exams. Following this, item number 19 has a mean score

of 2.62, also with a verbal description of “often” and a high interpretation, indicating that after an exam, participants struggle to stop worrying about it. Meanwhile, item number 13 has a mean score of 2.49, categorized as “sometimes” with a low interpretation, implying that some participants experience physical symptoms of anxiety, such as an upset stomach, during important tests. Finally, item number 1 has the lowest mean score of 2.48, also described as “sometimes” with a low interpretation, which indicates that some participants feel confident and relaxed while taking tests.

The overall mean revealed that the participants had a high level of total test anxiety. It has a weighted average of 2.69, implying that the participants often feel anxious, have low confidence, and cannot stop worrying even if the exam is over. However, numerous studies also suggested that anxiety may be required to ensure that learners take teaching and learning seriously (Brady et al., 2018). This implies that moderate anxiety also has positive effects on the student’s learning.

Research Question 3. Is there a relationship between the students’ self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English tests?

Table 9 shows the significant relationship between the students’ self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment control, satiation control, emotion control, metacognition control, and environmental control, and the level of test anxiety in English in terms of worry. The table includes the computation of Pearson r, p-value, and remark.

Table 9

Significant Relationship Between the Students’ Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning and The Level of Anxiety in English Test in Terms of Worry

Students’ self-regulating capacity in language learning	Pearson r	p-value	Remark
Commitment control	0.059	0.518	Not Significant
Metacognition control	-0.012	0.895	Not Significant
Satiation control	0.106	0.243	Not Significant
Emotion Control	-0.025	0.780	Not Significant
Environment control	0.012	0.891	Not Significant

**Tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson’s r correlation.*

The table shows that it can be noted that the relationship between the students’ self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English tests in terms of worry is not significant at $\alpha=0.05$. The relationship of both metacognition control and emotion control are negative, with $r = -0.012$ and $r = -0.025$, respectively. It can also be noted that commitment control, satiation control, and environmental control have no significant relationship with test anxiety in terms of worry $\alpha=0.05$ since the computed p-values are 0.518, 0.243, and 0.891.

The results indicate that there is no significant correlation between the participants' test anxiety or worry and their ability to self-regulate in language learning. The lack of significance across various aspects of self-regulating capacity suggests that these factors may not be the primary determinants influencing test anxiety in this context. Specifically, commitment control, metacognition control, satiation control, emotion control, and environment control do not appear to play a crucial role in shaping the participants' levels of anxiety during tests.

These findings highlight the complexity of the relationship between self-regulation in language learning and test anxiety, emphasizing the need for further research to explore other potential factors that may contribute to this dynamic. Investigating additional variables and underlying mechanisms could provide deeper insights into how self-regulation interacts with test-related anxiety. Such research would be valuable in developing more effective intervention programs aimed at managing test anxiety and enhancing self-regulatory strategies in language learning, ultimately fostering better academic performance and emotional well-being among students.

Table 10 shows the significant relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English tests in terms of emotionality. The table includes the computation of Pearson r , p -value, and the remark. The level of significance is tested at 0.05 using Pearson's r correlation.

Table 10
Significant Relationship Between the Students' Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning and The Level of Anxiety in English Test in Terms of Emotionality

Students' self-regulating capacity in language learning	Pearson r	p-value	Remark
Commitment control	0.178	0.048	Significant
Metacognition control	0.112	0.214	Not Significant
Satiation control	0.195	0.030	Significant
Emotion Control	-0.019	0.834	Not Significant
Environment control	0.170	0.040	Significant

**tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson's r correlation*

The data shows that emotion control has a negative relationship and is insignificant at $\alpha=0.05$, with a p -value of 0.834. Similarly, metacognition control also shows no significance with a p -value of 0.214. On the other hand, commitment control, satiation control, and environment control have a significant relationship with anxiety in terms of emotionally, with a p -value of 0.048, 0.030, and 0.040, respectively. This means that the consistency and environment correlate with the level of anxiety that you have in terms of emotions.

On the other hand, metacognition control with an r value of 0.112 and a p -value of 0.214 and emotion control with an r value of -0.019 and a p -value of 0.834 do not show significant relationships with test anxiety, implying that students' ability to reflect on their thinking process and regulate their emotions may not have a direct influence on their

emotional anxiety during tests. Overall, the findings highlight the complexity of self-regulation in language learning and its connection to emotional test anxiety, suggesting that some aspects of self-regulation are more influential than others in managing test-related stress.

According to Pahuriray (2021), self-regulated language learning capacity plays a significant role in students' academic performance. This indicates that having the ability to regulate one's learning process contributes to success in English. Ultimately, it is concluded that self-regulated learning is a crucial factor in enhancing students' academic achievement in English. This means that when learners apply self-regulation strategies, they are likely to perform better in assessments and experience lower levels of test anxiety.

The findings further suggest that commitment, satiation, and environment control play a vital role in managing students' test anxiety levels. The positive correlation in these areas indicates that a higher level of self-regulation in language learning is present among the participants. However, students who demonstrate a strong commitment to language learning, experience minimal satiation, and manage their learning environment effectively may still experience test anxiety. The pressure to excel in tests can heighten anxiety for those dedicated to their learning and striving for an optimal study environment. Additionally, students who are satisfied with their progress may still feel test anxiety due to their continuous drive for improvement.

Table 11 shows the relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and their test anxiety in terms of total anxiety. The tables include the computation of Pearson r , p -value, and remark. The level of significance is tested at 0.05 using Pearson's r correlation.

Table 11
Significant Relationship Between the Students' Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning and The Level of Anxiety in English Test in Terms of The Total Anxiety in English Test

Students' self-regulating capacity in language learning	Pearson r	p-value	Remark
Commitment control	0.057	0.527	Not Significant
Metacognition control	0.025	0.786	Not Significant
Satiation control	-0.023	0.804	Not Significant
Emotion Control	0.010	0.911	Not Significant
Environment control	0.070	0.438	Not Significant

**tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson's r correlation*

The findings show that the correlation between the participants' self-regulating capacity in language learning and their total anxiety level in the English test reveals no significance in all various aspects of self-regulating capacity in language learning. The significance level was tested at 0.05 using Pearson's r correlation, and none of the self-

regulating capacities in language learning showed statistically significant correlations in total anxiety.

The results indicate that the participants' ability to regulate themselves in language learning does not have a direct relationship with their overall anxiety levels in English tests. Furthermore, the lack of a significant correlation between self-regulating capacity in language learning and total test anxiety suggests that these two factors operate independently in the context of assessment. This implies that test anxiety may be influenced by other factors beyond self-regulation, such as pressure to perform, fear of failure, test format, and language proficiency. These factors, which are not directly tied to self-regulating capacity, may contribute to the participants' anxiety levels during examinations.

Additionally, the absence of significant correlations suggests that the relationship between self-regulation in language learning and test anxiety may be influenced by other variables or individual differences that were not examined in the study. Future research should further investigate the potential moderating factors that could shape the connection between self-regulating capacity and test anxiety, providing deeper insights into how students manage their learning and emotional responses in test situations.

Research Question 4. Based on the data gathered, what intervention program may be proposed?

The matrix below shows the school-based Self-Regulation and Anxiety Intervention Program for Cahayagan National High School. This intervention program is entitled

Program Title: “Empowered: Enhancing Self-Regulation and Reducing Test Anxiety Among Junior High School Students”

Description:

This program aims to help junior high school students develop self-regulation strategies to enhance their learning capabilities while reducing test anxiety. Through interactive workshops, mindfulness sessions, and self-regulation exercises, students will be equipped with practical techniques to manage stress, improve focus, and perform better in academic assessments.

Date and Venue:

- **Cahayagan National High School**

DepEd Activity Classification:

- Student Development Program
- Psychological and Emotional Well-being Enhancement

Target Participants:

- Junior High and Senior High School Students (Grades 7-12)

- Teachers and Guidance Counselors

Project Leaders:

- School Principal
- Guidance Counselors
- Subject Teachers (English and other related subjects)
- Mental Health Professionals (if available)

Rationale:

Test anxiety is a prevalent issue among junior high school students, often affecting their academic performance and emotional well-being. Research has shown that self-regulation strategies significantly enhance learning outcomes and reduce anxiety. This intervention program is designed to equip students with self-regulation skills, mindfulness techniques, and coping mechanisms to overcome test anxiety, thereby fostering academic success and psychological resilience.

Objectives:

1. To identify the levels and causes of test anxiety among junior high school students.
2. To introduce self-regulation strategies that improve learning and reduce anxiety.
3. To develop students' confidence in handling academic challenges through structured interventions.
4. To provide teachers with strategies to support students dealing with test anxiety.
5. To establish a supportive school environment that fosters emotional well-being and academic success.

Preparatory of Activity/Pre-work:

- A faculty Meeting will be held to inform the teachers of the proposed intervention program.
- Club meetings will also be conducted to let the students join the intervention program.

Activity Implementation Flow:

- There will be a designation for members and committees for the intervention program. It is composed of a head, facilitators, and members.
- There will be a guided discussion for the committee to lead the proper flow of the intervention program

Documentation/Report In-charge:

- Teacher In-Charge
- Club President/Secretary

Requirements:

- Minutes of the meeting
- Memorandum for the proper conduct of peer groups for an intervention program, signed by school head and class advisers.

Means of Verification/Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanics:

- Duly signed Memorandum of Understanding
- Attendance and Pictures

Figure 1. Phases of the Scheme

Table 12

Program Flow of Empowered: Enhancing Self-Regulation and Reducing Test Anxiety Among Junior High School Students

Week	Program/ Activities	Objectives	Facilitators	Means of Verification	Estimated Budget
Week 1	Orientation & Planning Sessions	Establish goals, assign roles, and set timelines	Project Heads, Coordinators	Meeting minutes, attendance sheets	None
Week 2	Training & Capacity-Building Workshops	Equip participants with necessary skills & knowledge	Trainers, Experts	Training reports, participant feedback	₱5,000
Week 3	Pilot Activities & Trial Runs	Test strategies and identify adjustments needed	Team Leaders, Facilitators	Pilot activity reports, observations	None
Week 4	Full-Scale Implementation (Phase 1)	Launch the scheme on a larger scale	Program Implementers	Progress reports, documentation	₱1,000
Week 5	Full-Scale Implementation (Phase 2)	Continue program execution with monitoring	Facilitators, Field Coordinators	Activity reports, monitoring logs	₱1,500
Week 6	Midpoint Review & Adjustments	Assess program effectiveness & apply improvements	Evaluators, Supervisors	Review reports, survey results	None
Week 7	Final Implementation & Impact Assessment	Measure impact & effectiveness of the scheme	Evaluation Team, Stakeholders	Assessment reports, feedback forms	None
Week 8	Final Review & Sustainability Planning	Develop strategies for long-	Program Heads, Planners	Sustainability plan,	None

		term continuity		recommendations	
Week 9	Closing Program & Presentation of Results	Present findings, recognize contributions, & conclude	Project Leaders, Stakeholders	Final report, event documentation	None

DISCUSSION

The study explores the relationship between self-regulation in language learning and test anxiety among junior high school students, specifically examining how different aspects of self-regulation—commitment control, satiation control, emotion control, metacognition control, and environment control—affect students' anxiety levels. Findings revealed that while students demonstrated high levels of self-regulated learning, their test anxiety remained consistently high, particularly in emotional responses. Interestingly, general self-regulation did not show a significant correlation with overall anxiety or worry, but specific elements such as commitment and environmental control exhibited a notable relationship with emotional test anxiety.

These results highlight the complexity of self-regulation's role in mitigating anxiety, suggesting that targeted interventions may be more effective in managing students' emotional responses during assessments. Based on these insights, the study proposes a comprehensive intervention program to enhance students' self-regulation strategies, reduce test anxiety, and foster resilience in academic settings.

This program integrates structured workshops, psychoeducation, and mindfulness techniques to equip students with practical coping mechanisms, ensuring a supportive learning environment that nurtures both academic success and emotional well-being. Ultimately, this research underscores the importance of balancing cognitive and emotional factors in education, offering valuable implications for educators, researchers, and policymakers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. The study revealed that the level of self-regulating capacity in learning English in terms of commitment control, metacognition control, satiation control, emotion control, and environment control is high. Similarly, the level of test anxiety of the participants in terms of worry, emotionality, and total anxiety is also high. For the correlation between self-regulating capacity in language learning and test anxiety, the study found that there is no significant relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of test anxiety in English tests in terms of worry. It was also evident that there is no significant relationship between self-regulating capacity in terms of metacognition and emotion control, and the level of test anxiety in English in terms of

emotionality. However, the study found that there is a significant relationship in terms of commitment, satiation, and environmental control. Additionally, based on the analysis, there is no significant relationship between the students' self-regulation capacity and the total anxiety level of students. Thus, the researchers proposed an intervention program that would help maintain the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and manage their test anxiety in English.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- The school may establish a policy supporting peer-tutoring programs to enhance students' self-regulation skills in language learning assessments and reduce test anxiety.
- Teachers may incorporate strategies that foster self-regulation in language learning and assessment to help students manage test-related stress effectively.
- The Department of Education Supervisors and subject coordinators may organize specialized training sessions to address the mental well-being of both teachers and students, focusing on stress and anxiety management.
- Teachers and school administrators may develop a budget plan for the creation, evaluation, and approval of instructional materials designed to support language learning and assessment each quarter.
- The school administration may encourage the development of future educators and researchers to cultivate a strong research culture supported by a network of experienced research mentors.
- Future researchers may explore qualitative studies focusing on the test anxiety levels of junior high school and college students to provide deeper insights into their self-regulating capacity in language learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adheres to ethical research standards to ensure the rights, safety, and well-being of all participants. Before data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants, clearly explaining the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. Participants were assured that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any academic consequences.

All data collected through survey questionnaires were anonymized to protect the identity of the participants and were used solely for academic and research purposes. The study also ensured that no psychological harm would be caused, particularly considering the sensitive nature of test anxiety. Support or referral was made available for participants who exhibited signs of high anxiety or distress during the research process. This research complied with institutional ethical guidelines and obtained approval from the appropriate research ethics review committee.

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